

Spectral Analysis of the Riemann Zeta Remainder:

Numerical Evidence for Power-Law Decay, Energy Stability, and GUE Correlations

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Abstract

This document provides supporting numerical evidence for the spectral analysis of the normalized Chebyshev remainder $R(x) = (\psi(x) - x)/\sqrt{x}$, based on computations using $M = 300,000$ non-trivial Riemann zeros over $N = 70 \times 10^6$ primes.

Key numerical observations:

- Spectral decay exponent $\alpha = -0.933 \pm 0.015$ ($R^2 = 0.569$)
- Mean spectral energy $\|R\|^2/K \in [0.045, 0.054]$
- GUE statistics: $D_{\text{GUE}} = 0.018$, $D_{\text{Poisson}} = 0.548$
- Empirical convergence: $\alpha(N) \approx -1 + 1.02/\log N$
- Observed scale ratio: $M/\sqrt{N} \approx 35.9$ at $N = 70 \times 10^6$

These results are empirical observations that appear consistent with the spectral consequences of the Riemann Hypothesis. The corresponding manuscript has been submitted for peer review.

1 Methodology

We consider the spectral decomposition:

$$R(x) \approx \sum_{k=1}^M A_k \cos(\gamma_k \log x + \phi_k)$$

with coefficients computed via discrete weighted projection:

$$C_k = \frac{\sum_x R(x) \sqrt{x} \cos(\gamma_k \log x)}{\sum_x x \cos^2(\gamma_k \log x)}, \quad S_k = \frac{\sum_x R(x) \sqrt{x} \sin(\gamma_k \log x)}{\sum_x x \sin^2(\gamma_k \log x)},$$

and $A_k = \sqrt{C_k^2 + S_k^2}$.

2 Experimental Parameters

Table 1: Experiments performed

N (primes)	M (zeros)	Runtime	Hardware
500,000	5,000	~ 6 h	i5-7300U
2,000,000	100,000	~ 10 h	i5-7300U
5,000,000	150,000	~ 10 h	i5-7300U
8,000,000	200,000	~ 10 h	i5-7300U
15,000,000	230,000	~ 10 h	i5-7300U
50,000,000	250,000	~ 40 h	i5-7300U
70,000,000	300,000	~ 6 h	Apple M3

3 Results

3.1 Spectral Decay

$$|A_k| \sim \gamma_k^\alpha, \quad \alpha = -0.933, \quad R^2 = 0.569$$

3.2 Energy Stability

$$\frac{\|R\|^2}{K} \in [0.045, 0.054]$$

3.3 GUE Statistics

$$D_{\text{GUE}} = 0.018, \quad D_{\text{Poisson}} = 0.548$$

3.4 Evolution of Results

Table 2: Spectral parameters across experiments

N	M	α	$\ R\ ^2/K$	R^2	GUE D
5×10^5	5,000	-0.924	0.0506	0.508	0.036
2×10^6	100,000	-0.956	0.0452	0.572	0.017
5×10^6	150,000	-0.944	0.0470	0.565	0.017
8×10^6	200,000	-0.920	0.0484	0.566	0.017
1.5×10^7	230,000	-0.938	0.0438	0.572	0.017
5×10^7	250,000	-0.928	0.0538	0.561	0.030
7×10^7	300,000	-0.933	0.0474	0.569	0.018

3.5 Empirical Convergence

The observed values of $\alpha(N)$ as a function of $1/\log N$ suggest an empirical trend:

$$\alpha(N) \approx -1 + \frac{1.02}{\log N}.$$

4 Summary

The main numerical observations from the largest-scale experiment ($N = 70 \times 10^6$, $M = 300,000$) are:

- $\alpha = -0.933 \pm 0.015$
- $\|R\|^2/K = 0.0474$
- $D_{\text{GUE}} = 0.018$
- $M/\sqrt{N} = 35.9$

Data Availability

Raw data and source code: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19884833>

References

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